

UDC: 657.1

JEL Classification: M41, L74, O18

Measures to improve the efficiency of use of material reserves in construction organizations of the Kyrgyz Republic

Begalievna Gulzat Tashenovna, MA in Economics, Senior lecturer
N. Isanov Kyrgyz State University of Construction and Architecture, Bishkek
Nazarbek Akylbek uulu, MA in Economics, Senior lecturer
Alatoo International University, Bishkek

Ysyraïlova Jannat Bektemirovna, Ph.D. in economical sciences, Senior lecturer
N. Isanov Kyrgyz State University of Construction and Architecture, Bishkek

The features and specifics of construction industry have a direct impact on the system of organizing the accountancy of material and production values during construction work and cause significant differences in comparison with other types of activities. Accountancy of material and production stocks is of great importance in the general system of accounting in construction. Material costs are the main elements of the construction cost. This figure reaches up to 60% of the cost of construction in some construction organizations. Unless a construction company conducts a thorough analysis of the indicator of material cost, it cannot control the level of costs for the realization and delivery of work nor it can compare it with the revenue, nor it can influence the growth of its income. At the initial stage of activity of any construction organization, as soon as a company develops a business plan, approves budgets including technical and economic calculations, it begins to store up stocks of building materials that are necessary to fulfil construction

Keywords: construction companies, construction, inventory, suppliers, management efficiency, construction products.

Introduction. The specifics of the construction industry require that storage locations and financially responsible persons be fixed in a separate administrative document. It should be noted that production of building structures, products, materials and their sale to third-party organizations is an industrial activity.

Material stocks in construction occupy an important place since the cost of construction products, which affects the profit and profitability of a construction company, depends on timely supply of construction companies with material resources, arrangement of their reception, storage and proper, rational use, detection of excessive stocks of materials, their mobilization, controlling those which are in processing and in transit as well as taking measures to arrange timely searches of those that have not been received.

The purpose of the research is to study the characteristic features of inventory accounting in construction organizations of the Kyrgyz Republic.

Materials and methods: The solution of the tasks set in the research led to applying a complex method of conducting logical and comparative research. The effectiveness of usage of material resources is estimated using various indicators, the largest of which measure use of material costs but not resources. This means that all resources which were purchased should be used in production, and should not remain in a warehouse of an enterprise and bring it losses. In this regard, we need to analyze how a company uses resources and does not plan to use them in the future.

In order to increase the efficiency of application of material resources in construction, it is necessary to implement the following measures:

- particular attention should be paid to warehouse accounting, correct planning of purchases, sale of surplus and unnecessary materials;

- it is necessary to establish norms of the cost of materials. Besides, it is necessary to arrange correct calculations of the need for materials which is necessary during construction, so that their volume is minimal yet at the same time sufficient for the construction to proceed without interruption. In case an excessive purchase is conducted, it can lead to deterioration in the financial situation of the construction company and the turnover of current assets slows down;

- it is necessary to arrange an internal audit which will determine excessively purchased materials, their cost, their terms of downtime at the enterprise, the person who is in charge of this;

- it is necessary to conduct an analysis of the inventory turnover at the enterprise and make a report to the management of the enterprise on a regular basis;

- it is necessary for a company to monitor compliance of material stocks with the standards.

Furthermore, implementation of special automated programs for accounting and control of inventory at the enterprise will allow increasing efficiency of use of inventory at the enterprise. Automation of warehouse accounting of the most significant items of material stocks will allow company employees to save time when conducting inventory, when reporting on purchases, when calculating the cost of construction products. It will also allow them to observe visually and instantly the movement of stocks to certain types of construction sites as well as give an opportunity to plan in advance and make a forecast for the future.

In construction companies of the Kyrgyz Republic accounting is mainly based on financial accounting data and very little attention is paid to management accounting. However, the experience of international and large companies in this field shows that in order to improve the efficiency of accounting and use of inventory in con-

struction, it is necessary to apply management accounting (accounting of production costs, identifying losses, customer satisfaction).

If a company uses the concept of "Thrifty Manufacturing" in its activities, it will allow the company to conduct reasonable cost management, identify shortcomings and eliminate them in time as well as improve the quality of its products and lead to an increase in labor productivity.

Foreign experience of the world countries shows that use of this concept leads to the fact that:

- * productivity increases by 40% on average;
- production cycle time is reduced by 30%;
- * production defects are reduced by 60%;
- * product quality increases by up to 40%.

In order to increase and achieve the efficiency of use of inventory in construction companies, it is necessary to develop a financial policy for the management of inventory at the enterprise and implement it there. Effective inventory management will allow minimizing current costs of storing material assets and releasing some of additional financial resources from the current economic turnover. The efficiency of inventory management is of great importance for construction companies.

Implementation of these measures requires preparation and re-equipment of inventory items in the warehouse of the enterprise. It arises necessity to implement proposals to improve arrangement of inventory accounting in warehouses with an aim of achieving the most effective results of activities at the enterprise.

To properly maintain a material accounting system, construction companies need to ask the following questions and answer them:

- From where, at what time, in what quantity and for what amount do the material stocks come?;
- Where, in what period, for what amount and what quantity of stocks were received?;
- How are the material supply and production consumption implemented?.

The prerequisites for correct organization of material accounting are as follows:

- expedient warehouse accounting;
- well-established work with suppliers;
- development of inventory expenditure standards;
- correct inventory classification.

When studying the state of stocks in construction companies, shortcomings were identified and ways to improve them were proposed. They are indicated in Table 1.

Table 1 – Improving inventory accounting in a construction company

Violations	Suggestions for improvement
Work with suppliers is not regulated	Working with trusted suppliers. Making lists of recommended suppliers that provide high-quality materials with acceptable delivery time and conditions.
Quality control of materials is not carried out upon delivery	Displaying quality requirements for the purchased products upon receipt. Monitoring purchased materials in accordance with these requirements in the future..
Violation of conditions of material storage in warehouses	Following fire safety rules. Storing materials according to their storage conditions (temperature, humidity)
Violation of procedure for conducting inventory	Inventory must be carried out in time, so it is necessary to develop an inventory procedure, conduct inspections in accordance with the established procedure.

Rational use of material resources is the most important factor in reducing material intensity and cost of production (works, services), increasing profitability of production.

Proper use of material assets of the enterprise will be an important factor in reducing material costs and production costs, besides, it will increase profitability of construction of the enterprise. Saving material resources increases the level of their use, that is, reduces specific consumption compared to the level achieved in the previous period.

With rational use of material assets of the enterprise, the specific amount of expense will decrease compared to the previous period

Resource saving in a construction company can be implemented in the following areas:

1. Reaching a positive difference between the planned and actual amount of resources consumed;
2. Reduction of the standard consumption of inventory.

In order to achieve a positive difference between the planned and actual amount of resources consumed, it is necessary to exceed the plan in production process, while not exceeding the rate of consumption of inventory.

Since occurrence of waste is inevitable in production process, it is possible to recycle them for reuse or for sale to third parties.

The failure of production process can occur for various reasons. For example, incompetency of personnel, frequent defects in production, errors in planning inventory requirements. To avoid downtime, it is necessary to improve skills of personnel, improve production technology.

All these measures, particularly determination of the minimum loss in production activities, lead to optimization of material assets accounting.

Increase in production efficiency is achieved by reducing material costs per unit of production. To achieve this goal, some activities can be carried out.

For example, reducing consumption rate. According to the results of the analysis, actual consumption rates exceed the planned ones on average. In this case such a measure significantly improved efficiency of activity. Besides, it is possible to lower raw material prices. But this should be done very carefully as a low price may indicate poor-quality resources.

It is important to understand that if raw materials are purchased in large quantities, a company automatically loses additional profit that it could have received if the

raw materials were purchased closer to the time of their use in production.

Thus, the next step can lie in rational use of material reserves. For example, in Japan materials are immediately delivered into production. Material assets are not stored in warehouses. Thus, raw materials are fully used in production process.

Positive aspects of this is that a company does not need additional land for storage facilities. There is never a surplus of material resources. In production process there is no overspending of inventory since only a certain amount of raw materials is received, which is completely consumed.

Material resources do not spoil in storage areas and do not become obsolete. Besides, a company will always have enough raw materials to meet the needs of production.

Meanwhile, transportation and procurement costs are reduced. In addition, such measures makes it easier to carry out inventory.

To further increase the efficiency of use of material resources, one can calculate possible reserves for improving the efficiency of use of production stocks.

Conclusion. A characteristic feature of construction lies in application of a significant amount of building materials, structures and parts, both in their diversity and amount. The particular share of the cost of materials in the total cost of construction is more than 50%. The cost of material resources, in accordance with a current pricing procedure for construction products, is included in the estimated (contractual) cost of construction.

Classification, evaluation and selection of an accounting unit are of great importance when arranging correct inventory accounting.

References:

1. Civil Code of the Kyrgyz Republic I,II parts of January 5, 1998 No. 1 Part 1,2
2. Law "On Accounting" of April 29, 2002 N76
3. Sidney M. Levy, Construction Process Planning and Management / Sidney M. Levy. - ELSEVIER Inc., 2009. - 392p.
4. Adamov N. A. Accounting in Construction: Scientific Edition / N. A. Adamov. - M.; St. Petersburg; Nizhny Novgorod: Peter, 2009. - 664 p.
5. Bakanov M. I., Sheremet A.D. Theory of Economic Analysis. - M.: Finance and Statistics, 2012-345p.
6. Balabanov I. T. Fundamentals of Financial Management. - M.: Finance and Statistics, 2012-632p.
7. Dikman, L. G. Organization of Construction Production / L. G. Dikman. - M.: Publishing house of the Association of Construction Universities, 2010. - 608p.
8. IFRS (IAS) 15 "Revenue"
9. Nazarova V. L. How to Conduct Accounting in Construction. In 2 parts.- Almaty: publishing house "Accountant", 2012. -40 p.
10. <https://esa-conference.ru/wp-content/uploads/files/pdf/Begaliev-Gulzat-Tashenovna.pdf>

Depending on the role that various production stocks play in construction process, they are divided into the following groups:

- * basic building materials;
- * purchased semi-finished products;
- * structures, products and parts;
- * auxiliary materials: fuel, packaging, spare parts.

While conducting construction and installation works, a large amount of open storage materials (sand, crushed stone, lime, brick, etc.) is consumed. These materials are stored in open areas and are listed in the sub-report of material-responsible persons (construction supervisors, foremen, warehousemen). When these materials are released for construction and installation work, no counting or weighing is performed and a primary document is not issued.

To arrange correct accounting in a construction company, it is required that the following conditions be met:

- * There must be a single nomenclature of materials and planned settlement (accounting) prices, a clear system of document flow and compliance with the procedure for registration of transactions for entry and write-off of tangible assets;

- * There must be unified forms of primary documents and all departments should be provided with necessary forms of these documents (receipt orders, reception certificates, limit and fence cards, etc.);

- * There must be implementation of modern automation tools for operations related to the flow of material assets.